

Synthesis and characterisation of some new heteropoly oxomolybdates containing two hetero atoms

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Sodium, potassium and ammonium salts containing two hetero atoms in 12 isopolyanion series have been prepared.

Tellurium having greater stability in its $[\text{TeO}_6]^{6-}$ form than $[\text{TeO}_4]^{2-}$ is capable of replacing one or more MO_6 to form a series of compounds of general formula, $[\text{M}^{x+1}\text{Te}_n\text{M}'_{12-n}\text{O}_{40}]^{(8-x)-}$, where M is any transition metal in +2 to +5 oxidation state and M' is vanadium, molybdenum or tungsten. EPR and ir spectra studies of ammonium salt of heteropoly molybdonickelate complexes have been reported¹. A number of mixed heteropoly oxometallates have been prepared². This communication reports sodium and potassium salts of mixed heteropolymolybdate with tellurium as hetero atom.

Results and Discussion

Sodium and potassium salts, namely, $\text{Na}_6[\text{CoTeMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 23\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_6[\text{CoTeMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Na}_6[\text{NiTeMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared at pH 3.43, 4.06 and 3.96 respectively. The position and assignments of main bands due to different types of metal-oxygen and water molecules are listed in Table 1.

The thermal studies of the compound revealed that all the compounds lose water of crystallization reflecting some endotherms. TGA data indicate the complete loss of water of crystallization at 553–573 K. Above 573 K, a plateau in the TG curve show gradual slow loss in weight. Decomposition above 623 ± 50 K was observed in all cases irrespective of salts. Above 873 K, slow volatilization of Mo_3 was observed. The analysis of residue indicated the

presence of mixed metal oxides. The insolubility of heated salt also confirmed the decomposition of heteropoly anionic cage.

Preliminary X-ray analysis of $\text{Na}_6[\text{CoTeMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 23\text{H}_2\text{O}$, revealed it to be cubic : $a = 13.39 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 13.73 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.55 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$; $V = 2491.10 \text{ \AA}^3$; $z = 2$; ρ calcd. = 3.244 g cm^{-3} , exptl. = 3.26 g cm^{-3} ; M_{obs} = 2446.08; M_{calcd} = 2433.81.

The apparent molecular weight of the compounds were determined by modified cryoscopic method using Na_2SO_4 , $10\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system. The value of anionic weight was found to be within $\pm 4\%$ from the theoretical value which is well within a range to predict the nature of anion to be monomeric.

Experimental

Sodium 11-molybdotellurocobaltate(II) : Cobaltous chloride, telluric acid and sodium molybdate were used in a ratio so that cobalt, tellurium and molybdenum are in the ratio of 1 : 1 : 11. Cobaltous chloride (1.07 g, 4.5 mmol) dissolved in water (25 cm^3) was gradually added dropwise to a solution (50 cm^3) of telluric acid (1.035 g, 4.5 mmol). The solution was warmed on a water-bath with stirring for ~2 h. Acetic acid was added to make the pH of the solution at 3.0–3.5. The mixture was added slowly in small instalments to an aqueous solution (150 cm^3) of sodium molybdate (12.1 g, 50 mmol) maintaining pH 3.4 with acetic

Table 1. Ir spectral data of heteropoly compounds $\text{M}''[\text{M}'\text{TeMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\text{H}_2\text{O}^*$

M''	M'	M	(Mo–O–Mo) ^a	(Mo–O) ^b	(Te–O) ^c	(M'–O) ^d	$\nu\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\delta\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\pi\text{H}_2\text{O}^d$
Na	Co	Mo	720	990 925 820	995	450	3435	1655	585
K	Co	Mo	610	920 810 760	980	435	3490	1665	590
Na	Ni	Mo	710	935 890 620	985	440	3430	1615	580

^aRef 3 ^bRef 4 ^cRef 5 ^dRefs. 3, 6

acid-sodium acetate buffer. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h and then evaporated over a water-bath to one-third of the original volume and allowed to crystallize. Resultant dark reddish brown crystals were washed with ethanol and analysed (Found : Na, 5.83; Co, 2.37; Te, 5.15; Mo, 43.92; H, 1.9; O, 40.83. $\text{Na}_6[\text{CoTeMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 23\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : Na, 5.67; Co, 2.42; Te, 5.24; Mo, 43.36; H, 1.89; O, 41.42%).

Potassium 11-molybdotellurocobaltate(II) : A hot aqueous solution (50 cm³) of cobaltous chloride (1.075 g, 4.5 mmol) was added slowly to a solution (50 cm³) of telluric acid (1.035 g, 4.5 mmol). This mixture was added 2 cm³ in each turn to a solution (100 cm³) containing potassium molybdate (11.9 g, 50 mmol) at pH 3.9–4.1 using acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer. The whole mixture was heated on a water-bath for 0.5 h and then refluxed for 3 h. The mixture was reduced to one-third of its original volume by heating. Dark reddish brown crystals that appeared after 5 days were washed with ether and analysed (Found : K, 8.95; Co, 2.10; Te, 4.82; Mo, 40.58; H, 2.01; O, 41.54. $\text{K}_6[\text{CoTeMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : K, 9.08; Co, 2.28; Te, 4.94; Mo, 40.83; H, 2.01; O, 40.86%).

Sodium 11-molybdotelluronickelate : Nickel chloride (0.525 g, 2.2 mmol) dissolved in water (25 cm³) was mixed to equal volume of aqueous solution of telluric acid (0.51 g, 2.2 mmol). The resultant mixture in small portions was added to an aqueous solution (100 cm³) containing sodium molybdate (6.0 g, 24.79 mmol). The pH was kept at 3.75–4.00. This mixture was refluxed, reduced to half of its original volume and left for crystallization. Greenish brown

solid was washed with alcohol and analysed (Found : Na, 5.65; Ni, 2.41; Te, 5.22; Mo, 44.87; H, 1.39; O, 40.46. $\text{Na}_6[\text{NiTeMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : Na, 5.89; Ni, 2.50; Te, 5.44; Mo, 45.03; H, 1.54, O, 39.60%).

AnalaR grade reagents were used. Sodium and potassium were estimated by flame photometry and AAS. C and H were estimated using a Coleman analyser. Mo, Te, Co and Ni were estimated using standard methods⁷. Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out on a STA-409 (Netzsch) analyser. X-Ray diffraction was recorded on a D500/501 (Siemens) instrument. IR spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP2000 spectrophotometer.

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References

1. B. E. Plyamovatiyi, I. I. Kalinichenko, M. Balyakovyy and F. A. Rozhdestvenskii, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1975, **20**, 1980.
2. L. C. W. Baker in "Advances in the Chemistry of Coordination Compounds", ed. G. Kischner, MacMillan, New York, 1961; S. K. Roy, R. Jaiswal and K. C. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **70**, 705; A. M. Quereshi, S. A. Zubairy and S. A. Malik, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 879; G. A. Tsigdinos, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Prod. Res. Dev.*, 1974, **13**, 267.
3. T. J. R. Weakley, *Struct. Bonding*, 1974, **13**, 583.
4. D. H. Brown, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **19**, 585.
5. G. A. Tsigdinos, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1970, **76**, 54.
6. M. T. Pope, "Heteropoly and Isopoly Oxometallates", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1983.
7. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, Green, London, 1971.